

HIGH TEMPERATURE CREEP OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The author started studying creep resistance of fibrous composites while working with Anthony Kelly in 1969 at NPL [1]. During the last 40 years he has been returning to that topic from time to time. This is because the topic is both scientifically interesting and obviously important from the practical point of view. In the last decade, with the developing single crystalline oxide fibres [2], which can be a base for heat-resistant composites, this work has been intensified to yield a sufficiently general understanding of creep behaviour of composites. In the present paper, this understanding is outlined.

Keywords: creep, metal matrix composites, oxide/oxide composites, oxide fibre, heat-resistant composites

INTRODUCTION

Fibrous composites exhibit various types of the creep behaviour depending on their microstructures and stress/temperature conditions. Development of heat-resistant composites needs normally a large bulk of the experimental work, which is inherently time-consuming. To decrease that bulk and speed up the development, it is necessary (i) to have micromechanical models of the creep behaviour of composites and (ii) to have a guide showing at a particular model to be applied to a particular composite under a particular set of the conditions. In the present paper, microstructural creep models are discussed on a background of a map of the creep regimes of composites. Results of creep experiments are also discussed by using the model considerations.

CREEP REGIMES

A composite with creeping matrix and initially continuous fibres can creep in the following four regimes:

1. **E**: Fibres are elastic and non-breaking.
2. **Br-NCr**: Fibres are elastic and brittle.
3. **Cr**: Fibres are creeping and non-breaking.
4. **Br-Cr**: Fibres are creeping and brittle.

If creep properties of the matrix and mechanical characteristics of the fibres (the Young's modulus and strength parameters) are known then dependencies of steady state creep rate on the composite stress can be easily written for regimes 2 to 4 provided mechanical behaviour of the fibre/matrix interface is also known [2,3]. It is important to note that the interface behaviour affects the mechanical properties of the composite constituents. This point is discussed in the full-text paper.

MAP OF CREEP REGIMES

Schematic of all creep regimes can be presented as a map shown in Fig. 1. Exact boundaries between the particular areas can be traced by applying both calculation and experimental measurements.

Fig. 1. A schematic map of the creep regimes of composites under homogeneous stress state.

Obviously, regime **E** looks favourably from the point of view of a material user; however, it can be observed at rather low stresses or/and low temperatures when the fibres neither break nor creep. The only important fibre characteristic is the Young's modulus in this case. Normally, one should be looking for heavier loading composites, which put fibres under conditions, in which they will be either fracturing by fragmentation or creeping, or even doing both. In the full-text paper some examples of the creep of oxide-fibre/Ni-based-matrix and oxide/oxide composites in all the regimes mentioned are given.

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References

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